

Investigation of the operation of an integrated UASB and subsurface flow constructed wetland system at ambient temperature for the treatment of domestic wastewater in remote areas

T. Seintos¹, A. Koukoura², E. Statoris¹, A. Rizzo³, R. Bresciani³, F. Masi³, D. Mamais¹, C. Noutsopoulos¹, A. S. Stasinakis², S. Malamis¹

¹Sanitary Engineering Laboratory, Department of Water Resources and Environmental Engineering, School of Civil Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, 5 Iroon Polytechniou, Zografou, 15780, Athens, Greece

²Water and Air Quality Laboratory, Department of Environment, University of the Aegean, 81100, Greece

³Iridra Srl, via la Marmora 51, Firenze 50121, Italy

Keywords: constructed wetlands, UASB, greenhouse gas emissions

Presenting author email: sei_taxiarchis@hotmail.com

Introduction

This work investigates the performance of the upflow anaerobic sludge blanket process coupled to a vertical subsurface flow constructed wetland for the treatment of domestic wastewater. It examines a number of parameters that vary due to seasonal variations such as temperature, flow rate, influent pollutant concentration/dilution (Fernández del Castillo et al., 2022) and the impact it has in the quality of the treated effluent. The treated effluent should meet the qualitative characteristics for unrestricted irrigation.

Materials & Methods

Two parallel UASB reactors were installed (48 m³ in total) and their effluent was then sent to a two-stage vertical flow CWs. The first stage CW consisted of a saturated bed (VSSF SAT; 250 m², gravel substrate, planted with *Phragmites australis*; continuous feeding), while the second was a biodiverse unsaturated bed (VSSF UNSAT; 600 m², gravel with intermediate sand filter, planted with *Typha latifolia*, *Juncus inflexus*, *Iris pseudacorus*, *Scirpus lacustris*; intermittent feeding). Finally, tertiary treatment was provided by UV disinfection. The UASB-CWs system could treat up to 100 m³/d.

Operation was divided in periods that were mainly characterized by the system flowrate (Q) and temperature (T) since it was the limiting factor for the ambient operation of the anaerobic treatment step (Table 1). Conventional pollutants were analyzed according to Standards Methods and greenhouse gases (GHGs) emitted from CWs were determined with an FTIR analyzer on-site using the closed hood method on representative points of both the VSSF unsaturated and saturated CW beds.

Results

The ambient UASB – vertical subsurface flow CW system achieved high performance in terms of suspended solids and COD removal (>98 & >92 %, respectively). Nitrogen and phosphorus removal was on average 26 and 23%, respectively; thus, significant nutrient concentrations were maintained in the UASB effluent. The biogas that was retrieved from the UASB varied with OLR and temperature, while under almost mesophilic conditions biogas yield was equal to 0.28 m³CH₄ kgCOD⁻¹_{rem.}

The two-step CW system revealed an increased buffering capacity when UASB performance was sub-optimal, with VSSF SAT acting as temporary solids' capture system and VSSF UNSAT providing final filtration, biodegradation and nitrification. Furthermore, GHG emissions analyses revealed that emissions vary in terms of daily mass flux with the CW type, loading rate, time in the case of intermittently fed unsaturated CW (Table 2); CH₄ emissions were found to be greater than those in literature – related to the dissolved methane contained in the UASB effluent – and N₂O-N emissions were found in some cases to be greater in the unsaturated CW than those in literature (Mander et al., 2014).

Conclusion

UASB coupled with CWs can provide high level of domestic wastewater treatment and, despite the challenge with diluted wastewater and ambient environment for the UASB, proper dimensioning of such a system provides a promising, low-cost regenerative solution for decentralized areas that can deliver reclaimed water suitable for unrestricted irrigation. As for GHGs from the CWs, a challenge remains due to the complexity of the system in terms of flow and processes patterns and detailed monitoring through various periods of the year is required for an estimation of annual CO₂, equivalent footprint.

Acknowledgements

This work has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776643 within the framework of HYDROUSA project.

Table 1. Operation parameters for the integrated UASB – CW system

Period	S	I	II	III	IV	
Days	1 - 119	120 - 266	267 – 373	374 - 416	417 - 448	449 - 654
Q_{in} ($m^3 d^{-1}$)	20.1 ± 8.3	$65.3 \pm 3.7.0$	25.2 ± 1.8	40.8 ± 3.0	59.2 ± 0.2	82 ± 7.9
Temperature ($^{\circ}C$)	22.0 ± 3.5	23.2 ± 3.5	13.5 ± 0.7	15.2 ± 1.7	19.0 ± 1.6	22.7 ± 3.8

Table 2. VSSF CW greenhouse gas emissions compared to literature

CW type	Period	CH_4-C^1	N_2O-N	CO_2-C
		($mg m^{-2} h^{-1}$)	($mg m^{-2} h^{-1}$)	($mg m^{-2} h^{-1}$)
VSSF UNSAT	High Q - sat bottom	2.3 ± 0.7	0.64 ± 0.37	162.0 ± 64.2
	Low Q - sat bottom	0.4 ± 0.1	0.27 ± 0.10	159.1 ± 60.8
<i>Mander et al. (2014)</i>	25-75% data range	2.0 – 4.0	0.04 - 0.20	120 - 210
VSSF SAT	High Q	153.4 ± 68.1	0.56 ± 0.32	253.1 ± 80.5
	Low Q	95.7 ± 44.9	0.06 ± 0.04	79.9 ± 47.5
<i>Mander et al. (2014)</i>	25-75% data range	3.0 – 12.0	0.02 - 0.40	120 - 210

Figure 1. Box – whisker plot on COD concentration in influent and after each treatment step

Figure 2. Ammonium removal in the VSSF CWs

References

- Fernández del Castillo, A., Garibay, M. V., Senés-Guerrero, C., Orozco-Nunnally, D. A., de Anda, J., & Gradilla-Hernández, M. S. (2022). A review of the sustainability of anaerobic reactors combined with constructed wetlands for decentralized wastewater treatment. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 371, 133428. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133428>
- Mander, Ü., Dotro, G., Ebbe, Y., Towprayoon, S., Chiemchaisri, C., Furlan, S., Jamsranjav, B., Kasak, K., Truu, J., Tournebize, J., & Mitsch, W. J. (2014). Greenhouse gas emission in constructed wetlands for wastewater treatment : A review. *Ecological Engineering*, 66, 19–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2013.12.006>

¹ CH_4 is related mostly to the UASB effluent fed in the CWs